

RESOLVING LEGALESE: A MULTILINGUAL EXPLORATION OF
NEGATION SCOPE RESOLUTION IN LEGAL DOCUMENTS

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ABSTRACT

Resolving the scope of a negation within a sentence is a challenging NLP task. The complexity of legal texts and the lack of annotated in-domain negation corpora pose challenges for state-of-the-art (SotA) models when performing negation scope resolution on multilingual legal data. Our experiments demonstrate that models pre-trained without legal data under perform in the task of negation scope resolution compared to cross-domain experiments conducted between different domains such as medical data and literary texts. We release a new set of annotated court decisions in German, French, and Italian and use it to improve negation scope resolution in both zero-shot and multilingual settings. We achieve a token-level F1-score of 86.7% in our zero-shot cross-lingual experiments, where the models are trained on two languages and evaluated on the third. Our multilingual experiments, where the models were trained on all available negation data and evaluated on our legal datasets, resulted in an F1-score of 91.1%.

Today is never too late to be brand new.
— Taylor Swift

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ACRONYMS

LM	language model
LMs	language models
RNN	recurrent neural network
BERT	Bidirectional Encoder Representation from Transformers
GPT	generative pre-training
SotA	state-of-the-art
NLP	natural language processing

INTRODUCTION

Negation scope resolution is an important research problem in the field of natural language processing (NLP). It describes the detection of words that are affected by a negation cue (e.g. no or not) in a sentence, which is important for understanding its true meaning. Although this task is far from trivial, deep learning approaches have shown promising results [19, 34, 35].

Figure 1: Overview of results over all experiments and selected models. For the detailed results see Appendix A.2

As with many NLP tasks, the largest amount of annotated data is available in English¹. Multilingual datasets are less common and often not easily accessible. For example, on the [huggingface hub](https://huggingface.co/datasets), one of the biggest open-source dataset libraries, 4559 datasets are tagged as English. The next most common language is Chinese with 10 times fewer datasets for a total of 469². In addition, much of the work conducted in the area of negation scope resolution has been done in the medical domain in order to automatically process clinical reports and discharge summaries [36]. Other datasets consist of literary texts [23] or more informal data such as online reviews [20]. The legal domain differs from all of the above in that it is often very complex (i.e., legalese) and uses highly specific vocabulary and knowledge that is not common outside the legal domain [13, 32]. This poses a challenge to any model tackling tasks in the legal domain. While a large amount of legal data is publicly available

¹ Mielke [22] analyzed all ACL conference proceedings from 2004, 2008, 2012, and 2016 and found that between 58% and 69% were evaluated only in English

² Numbers extracted from <https://huggingface.co/datasets> on 13.08.2023

and has been annotated for various tasks [3–5, 26–28, 31], to the best of our knowledge there exists no legal negation corpus.

We annotate four new datasets containing legal judgments from Swiss and German courts in German, French and Italian for negation cues and scopes. We find that these legal documents contain on average longer sentences as well as longer annotated negation scopes, compared to existing datasets. Our cross-domain zero-shot experiments show that the legal domain poses a significant challenge to models attempting negation scope resolution. The results achieved by models pre-trained in different domains are lower than those seen in other cross-corpus experiments [19, 35]. Using our newly annotated datasets, we were able to improve these results. Our models trained on our legal dataset achieve higher F1-Scores in zero-shot cross-lingual experiments than the models pre-trained only on different domains. By training on all available data, we are able to further improve these results, achieving F1-Scores around 90% for our multilingual experiments. Our results provide an interesting insight into how even smaller datasets can make a valuable contribution to improving the performance of language models (LMs) on a specific downstream task such as negation scope resolution.

1.1 CONTRIBUTIONS

The contributions of this paper are three-fold:

- We conduct a series of experiments to evaluate the performance of several multilingual LMs on negation scope resolution in law, a previously unstudied domain.
- We release new datasets of legal data annotated for negation in German, French, and Italian that each contain around 1000 sentences.
- We train and evaluate models on the task of negation scope resolution on the newly annotated datasets to provide a reference point and achieve token-level F1-scores in the mid eighties for cross-lingual zero-shot experiments and up to 91% in multilingual experiments.

2.1 THE TRANSFORMER

The transformer architecture is used by many state-of-the-art LMs and has advanced progress in many NLP tasks [7, 10]. It was introduced in 2017 by Vaswani et al. [37]. Its self-attention mechanism allows to capture long-range dependencies within texts which represents a great advantage over earlier architectures such as recurrent neural networks (RNNs). Transformers also require less training time because they are able to process all input tokens in parallel, while RNNs only process one word at the time. In the following sections we describe the model architecture of the transformer, illustrated in Figure 2 [37], which includes a detailed description of the self-attention mechanism that constitutes the most important layer of this architecture

2.1.1 Architecture

The transformer consist of an encoding and a decoding stack. In the original architecture described by Vaswani et al. [37], each stack contains 6 identical layers. Each encoder layer contains two sub-layers. The input is first fed through a multi-head self-attention mechanism described in detail in the next section. The second sub-layer is a fully connected feed-forward neural network. The decoder layer additionally includes an encoder-decoder attention layer between the other two sub-layers which performs multi-head self-attention on the output of the encoder stack. The self-attention layer of the decoder was slightly modified to only consider previous positions of the output sequence by masking subsequent positions.

The transformer applies residual connections [16] around each sub-layer, followed by layer normalization [2]. Residual connections alleviate the problem of vanishing gradients, a challenge often faced during the training of neural networks where the gradient of the loss function approaches zero and slows down the learning progress. With residual connections, the input of the sub-layer is added to its output which fixes this issue. The normalization layer normalizes this output and works to stabilize the activations of neurons in the neural network.

As input for the encoder and decoder stack, each token needs to be converted to a vector. The transformer uses learned embeddings to perform this operation. Because the transformer processes all input tokens at the same time, it needs a mechanism to provide additional information about the order of the input embeddings. To do so, positional encodings are added to the input embeddings. These encodings contain information about the position or distance between different tokens of the input sequence.

Figure 2: The transformer model architecture [37].

To convert the output of the final decoder layer from a vector into tokens, a linear layer is applied to project the output vector to a logits vector which gives the raw probabilities for each output token. Then a softmax function is applied to output the normalized next token predictions which can be used to select the predicted token.

2.1.1.1 Multi-Head Self-Attention

Self-attention includes information about other tokens in an input sequence in the representation of that token. To do this, a query, key, and value vector are calculated from the input embedding by multiplying it with three different weight matrices trained during the training process. To calculate the attention, a dot-product attention function combined with a scaling factor is used. First, the dot-product of the query vector with each key vector is calculated and each divided by the scaling factor $\sqrt{d_k}$ where d_k is the dimension of the key and query vectors. Then a softmax function is applied, which gives the normalized weights for each value. The sum of all weighted value vectors gives the output of the attention function. This function is not only applied to one input embedding at the time, but instead several keys, queries and values are computed into matrices and the function calculates a matrix output.

In the transformer, the attention function is calculated on h different projections of the keys, queries, and values. The outputs from all these heads are then concatenated and projected by multiplying them with a weight matrix trained by the model. This is described as the multi-head approach to self-

attention and has the advantage that the model can pay attention to different parts of the input sequence.

2.1.2 Use in Language Models

Since the introduction of the transformer architecture, it has been adapted by many state-of-the-art LMs. The OpenAI generative pre-training (GPT) transformer model [30] uses multi-layer decoders and is pre-trained on a variety of unlabeled text. It achieves very good results on zero-shot and few-shot learning results on many tasks.

The Bidirectional Encoder Representation from Transformers introduced by Devlin et al. [10] is a transformer model that uses an encoder stack to pre-train bidirectional representations. It was pre-trained on multiple tasks including masked language modeling and can be fine-tuned to a wide range of language understanding tasks on which it achieves SotA results.

2.2 RELATED WORK

In the past, different approaches have been used to address the issue of negation detection and negation scope resolution. Early research focused mainly on rule-based approaches. NegEx, a simple regular expression algorithm developed by Chapman et al. [6], was successfully able to identify negations in the medical domain. Morante, Liekens, and Daelemans [24] first introduced a machine learning system that tackles the task of negation scope resolution. They used two memory-based classifiers, one to identify the negation cue in a sentence, and one to identify the scope of the negation. On the negation scope resolution task, they achieved an F1-Score of 81% on the BioScope corpus [36]. These results were later surpassed by Fancellu et al. [12], achieving an F1-Score of 92% by using neural networks for scope detection. The best results on the BioScope corpus, as well as on two other publicly available negation corpora, the SFU Review Corpus [20] and the ConanDoyle-neg corpus [23], were achieved by Khandelwal and Sawant [19]. Their NegBERT model is based on Bidirectional Encoder Representation from Transformers (BERT) introduced by Devlin et al. [10] and applies a transfer learning approach for negation detection and scope resolution.

Only a limited amount of work has been conducted on negation scope resolution across different languages. Fancellu, Lopez, and Webber [11] developed a cross-lingual system, trained on English data and tested on a Chinese corpus. By employing cross-lingual universal dependencies in English they were able to achieve an F1-Score of 72% on the Chinese data. Shaitarova, Furrer, and Rinaldi [34] investigated cross-lingual zero-shot negation scope resolution between English, Spanish, and French. They built on NegBERT but used the multilingual BERT (mBERT) model. Shaitarova and Rinaldi [35] built on this using NegBERT with mBERT and XLM-R_{Large} [7], and were able to achieve a token-level F1-score of 87% on a zero-shot transfer from Spanish to Russian.

The sparse amount of cross-lingual research can be explained by the lack of annotated data in languages other than English. There are few corpora annotated with negations in German and Italian [18]. The only German corpus is the German negation and speculation corpus [8], a corpus of medical data and clinical notes which is not publicly available and for which no annotation guidelines are published. For Italian, Altuna, Minard, and Speranza [1] presented a framework for the annotation of negations and applied it to a corpus of news articles and tweets, parts of which are publicly available. In French, Dalloux et al. [9] annotated a medical corpus, available on request. To the best of our knowledge, there currently exists no legal corpus annotated with negations.

DATA

We annotated four new datasets in three languages for negation cues and scopes. We also standardized the existing French and English datasets to make them more accessible¹. Our datasets consist of publicly available legal judgments from Swiss and German courts. Since negation scope resolution is a sentence-level task, we split the data into sentences before annotation using sentence boundary annotations. The French (fr) and Italian (it) datasets consist of a subset of Swiss court decisions from the Swiss-Judgment-Prediction dataset [29] and the **Multi-Legal-Pile** [28] which were annotated for sentence spans by Brugger, Stürmer, and Niklaus [3]. The main German data (de (DE)) is a subset of judgments from German courts collected by Glaser, Moser, and Matthes [15] which was also standardized by Brugger, Stürmer, and Niklaus [3]. Only judgments were included in our dataset because they include a variety of sources and legal areas, they also have a higher density of negation cues compared to other legal texts, therefore negation scope resolution in judgment documents can give us a lot of valuable information. To validate that the negation scope prediction also works on German court data from Switzerland, we curated a small dataset of German-Swiss court decisions (de (CH)) that is also a subset of the Swiss-Judgment-Prediction corpus. We separated each dataset into a train (70%), test (20%), and validation (10%) split.

To ensure that sufficient negation data is available in each dataset, a negation score was assigned to each document based on a simple word search for the most common negation words in each language. The documents with the highest negation scores were then selected for annotation. Table 1 shows the amount of data and the distribution of negations for the newly created datasets in comparison to the existing datasets in English and French. Our datasets contain a slightly higher ratio of negated sentences compared to the other datasets. This can be attributed to the nature of legal data and our pre-selection procedure. Because we annotated only a subset of an existing corpus we were able to exclude documents without or only few negations while other corpora like ConanDoyle-neg and SFU annotated complete existing datasets or stories.

All annotations were carried out by human annotators in their native language using the annotation tool **Prodigy**. All annotators are university students but not part of a legal study program. The annotations were cross-checked by one annotator, who has a linguistic background, with the help of an online translator to ensure that they adhere to the annotation guidelines and are consistent across all three languages. The annotation guidelines are based on existing guidelines for the English datasets, and have been extended to cover all three different languages included in our data, as well as the char-

¹ All datasets are available at <https://huggingface.co/datasets/rcds/MultiLegalNeg>

	Dataset	Total	Negated	%neg
legal	fr	1059	382	36.07
	it	1001	418	41.76
	de (DE)	1098	454	41.35
	de (CH)	208	112	53.85
external	SFU	17672	3528	19.96
	BioScope	14700	2095	14.25
	ConanDoyle-neg	5714	1421	24.87
	Dalloux	11032	1817	16.47

Table 1: Total number of sentences, and number and percentage of sentences containing at least one negation.

acteristics of the legal domain². Some of the most important guidelines are summarized below.

NEGATION CUES Cues were not annotated as part of the negation scope as documented in the annotation guidelines for the ConanDoyle-neg corpus [25]. We did not include affixal cues³ in our annotations and kept all annotations to the word as the level of the minimal syntactic unit.

MULTIPLE NEGATIONS Annotators were instructed to annotate one negation per sentence. Sentences containing multiple negations were duplicated prior to annotation based on the most common negation cues. To ensure that the same cue was not annotated twice, the duplicates were displayed next to each other in the annotation tool to allow the annotators to see which clues had yet to be annotated.

MAXIMUM SCOPE STRATEGY As with BioScope, a maximum scope strategy was used. This means that the scope extends to the largest possible unit. If a negated clause has subordinate clauses that add additional information to the clause, the scope extends over the negated clause and all of its subordinate clauses, as illustrated in 1. (in this and further examples, the cue is marked in **bold** while scope is underlined). This sentence structure is very common in our set of legal data.

1. Vorliegend ginge es **nicht** darum, dass ein Arbeitgeber über Fristen oder Pflichten nicht aufgeklärt habe, somit eine blosse Untätigkeit des Arbeitgebers [...]

*In the present case, it was **not** a matter of an employer not having provided information about deadlines or obligations, thus a mere inactivity on the part of the employer [...].*

² The annotation guidelines as well as the code to pre-train our models can be found here: https://github.com/RamonaChristen/Multilingual_Negation_Scope_Resolution_on_Legal_Data

³ Affixal cues are cues within a word such as impossible

COURT CITATIONS Our dataset contains two main types of citations: inline citations and parenthesized citations. Inline citations, as in 2. were annotated as part of the scope, while parenthesized citations, as in example 3., were excluded from the negation scope.

2. Da der Kläger **kein** ähnlicher leitender Angestellter i.S.d 14 Abs. 2Satz 2 KSchG ist [...]

*Since the plaintiff is **not** a similar executive employee in the sense of 14 Abs. 2Satz 2 KSchG [...]*

3. Seit dem 06.02.2017 ist der Kläger im Handelsregister **nicht mehr** als Geschäftsführer eingetragen (vgl. Auszug aus dem Handelsregister in Anlage K9, Bl 75 ff. d.A).

*Since 06.02.2017 the plaintiff is **no longer** registered in the commercial register as managing director (see extract from the commercial register in annex K9, Bl 75 ff. d.A)*

PUNCTUATION Punctuation marks, such as periods or exclamation points, were excluded from the scope, unless the scope spans multiple clauses separated by commas.

Table 2 shows the average number of tokens in a sentence for all datasets as well as the average length of the annotated scopes as a ratio between annotated and not annotated tokens. On average, the sentences in our legal datasets are slightly longer than in other datasets. Furthermore, the mean length of the annotated scopes in our data is higher than in all other datasets. For de (DE), over 50 percent of tokens were annotated as scope, which is around twice as much as with the biomedical, literary, and review corpora. This can be attributed to the sentence structure in the legal domain as well as our annotation guidelines (e.g., we annotated the subject as part of the scope). Moreover, nested sentences with many subordinate clauses are very common in our dataset. In conjunction with our maximum scope strategy, this results in longer scopes compared to other datasets.

	Dataset	Sentence	Scope
legal	fr	48.52	37.96%
	it	40.84	30.17%
	de (DE)	31.14	50.18%
	de (CH)	27.65	36.03%
external	SFU	24.46	21.87%
	BioScope	28.49	25.91%
	ConanDoyle-neg	22.11	32.37%
	Dalloux	25.96	19.82%

Table 2: The average number of tokens per sentence. Scopes are shown as a percentage of negated tokens.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

We conducted a series of experiments to evaluate the performance of negation scope resolution models on our multilingual legal data. We use the NegBERT architecture [19] because it achieved the best results for negation scope resolution on existing datasets and combined it with a number of pre-trained multilingual LMs outlined in Table 3.

Model	Source	InLen	Params	Vocab	Steps	BS	Corpus	Langs
DistilmBERT	Sanh et al. [33]	512	134M	120K	n/a	< 4000	Wikipedia	104
mBERT	Devlin et al. [10]	512	177K	120K	n/a	< 4000	Wikipedia	104
XLM-R _{Base/Large}	Conneau et al. [7]	512	278M/560M	250K	1.5M	8192	2.5TB CC100	100
Glott500-m	ImaniGooghari et al. [17]	512	395M	401K	480K	384	glot500-c	511
Legal-Swiss-R _{Base/Large}	Rasiah et al. [31]	512	184M/435M	128K	1M/500K	512	CH Rulings/Legislation	3
Legal-XLM-R _{Base/Large}	Niklaus et al. [28]	4096	184M/435M	128K	1M/500K	512	CH Rulings/Legislation	3

Table 3: Model stats. InLen: max input length during pre-training. Params: total parameter count. BS: batch size.

All experiments were conducted with the same hyperparameters, which were optimized with a search over learning rates 5e-7, 1e-6, 3e-6, 1e-5, 3e-5, 5e-5 and batch sizes 4, 8, 16, 32, 64, and 128. We optimized the hyperparameters for mBERT and XLM-R and concluded that the best results can be achieved with an initial learning rate of 1e-5 and a batch size of 16. To avoid overfitting, we employed an early stopping method with patience set to 8 as a compromise between the patience of 6 used in the original NegBERT experiments [19] and 9 used in the multilingual experiments of Shaitarova and Rinaldi [35]. The maximum input length was increased to 252 tokens to fit our data. We ran each experiment five times with different random seeds and report the mean token-level F1-score averaged over random seeds, as well as the standard deviation.

In a first experiment, all models were trained on the entirety of the existing French and English datasets and evaluated on our new legal datasets. This represents a zero-shot transfer learning approach across different domains as well as different languages for the evaluation on the German and Italian datasets. For a second series of zero-shot experiments, we attempted a cross-lingual transfer within our legal datasets. For each cross-lingual experiment, the models were trained on two of the languages in the dataset and evaluated on the dataset in the third language. We also conducted multilingual experiments using our datasets as well as all available data. Lastly, we evaluated the performance of ChatGPT in zero- and few-shot experiments.

RESULTS

5.1 ZERO-SHOT CROSS-DOMAIN TRANSFER

The results for our zero-shot cross-domain transfer experiments are presented in Table 4. The best results over all datasets were achieved by the Legal-XLM-R_{Large} model, which scored a token-level F1-score of 71.6%. Overall, the LMs pre-trained on legal data demonstrated a 4-percentage-point advantage, with a mean F1 of 68.3%, compared to the other models pre-trained on different domains. In general, the cross-domain transfer into the legal domain is not as successful as other zero-shot experiments across different languages and domains conducted by other researchers (i.e., Khandelwal and Sawant [19] and Shaitarova, Furrer, and Rinaldi [34]) which indicates that the cross-domain transfer from the non-legal domain to the legal domain is not trivial.

Model	Test Dataset				Mean F1 by Model
	fr	it	de (DE)	de (CH)	
DistilmBERT	61.43 \pm 1.9	63.40 \pm 2.6	63.50 \pm 4.3	58.78 \pm 4.5	61.78 \pm 3.8
mBERT	66.39 \pm 2.1	68.49 \pm 0.8	64.17 \pm 3.1	54.31 \pm 4.8	63.34 \pm 6.2
XLM-R _{Base}	66.80 \pm 1.9	71.40 \pm 0.8	67.29 \pm 3.7	62.44 \pm 2.9	66.98 \pm 4.0
XLM-R _{Large}	72.30 \pm 2.0	70.30 \pm 0.9	73.81 \pm 4.2	63.72 \pm 4.6	70.03 \pm 5.0
Glott500-m	63.78 \pm 0.8	65.54 \pm 1.1	61.38 \pm 4.0	54.51 \pm 2.5	61.30 \pm 4.9
Legal-Swiss-R _{Base}	69.48 \pm 2.3	68.64 \pm 1.0	71.81 \pm 3.8	54.26 \pm 4.9	66.05 \pm 7.7
Legal-Swiss-R _{Large}	74.66 \pm 2.4	72.68 \pm 1.5	76.5 \pm 1.6	51.75 \pm 6.6	68.89 \pm 10.8
Legal-XLM-R _{Base}	71.50 \pm 3.1	71.48 \pm 2.2	71.35 \pm 5.4	51.93 \pm 3.5	66.57 \pm 9.3
Legal-XLM-R _{Large}	74.52 \pm 2.1	74.48 \pm 3.3	76.06 \pm 3.3	61.30 \pm 8.9	71.59 \pm 7.7
<i>ChatGPT</i>	13.00 \pm 2.1	25.11 \pm 1.5	16.47 \pm 2.6	32.91 \pm 7.9	21.87 \pm 8.9
Mean F1 by Dataset	68.99 \pm 4.9	69.60 \pm 3.7	69.54 \pm 6.4	57.00 \pm 6.4	66.28 \pm 7.6

Table 4: Cross-domain zero-shot results from existing datasets to our new legal datasets. All models except for ChatGPT were pre-trained on all external datasets, ChatGPT did not receive any training data. The bottom right entry shows the average across all datasets and models except ChatGPT.

5.2 ZERO-SHOT CROSS-LINGUAL TRANSFER

Table 5 presents the results of our zero-shot cross-lingual experiments conducted with only our legal datasets. Although these datasets are considerably smaller than the existing English and French datasets, we were able to increase the F1-score by an average of 15.6% across all models and datasets. The legal models still performed well in these experiments, but they no longer

Model	Test Dataset				Mean F1 by Model
	fr	it	de (DE)	de (CH)	
DistilmBERT	79.56 \pm 1.0	74.94 \pm 1.7	58.74 \pm 9.6	52.59 \pm 11.3	66.46 \pm 13.3
mBERT	87.22 \pm 1.6	81.94 \pm 1.3	81.39 \pm 3.6	70.78 \pm 6.7	80.33 \pm 7.1
XLM-R _{Base}	88.70 \pm 0.8	86.43 \pm 2.2	88.00 \pm 1.9	83.71 \pm 4.8	86.71 \pm 3.3
XLM-R _{Large}	90.55 \pm 0.9	84.93 \pm 1.7	91.36 \pm 0.8	76.65 \pm 4.5	85.87 \pm 6.4
Glott500-m	86.77 \pm 2.3	83.41 \pm 1.3	90.10 \pm 2.0	77.73 \pm 4.6	84.50 \pm 5.4
Legal-Swiss-R _{Base}	87.42 \pm 1.2	84.54 \pm 1.6	88.24 \pm 1.0	70.95 \pm 3.6	82.79 \pm 7.4
Legal-Swiss-R _{Large}	84.63 \pm 1.0	83.88 \pm 1.9	88.47 \pm 3.9	70.33 \pm 6.0	81.83 \pm 7.8
Legal-XLM-R _{Base}	86.40 \pm 2.1	83.28 \pm 1.4	89.56 \pm 2.5	74.52 \pm 8.0	83.44 \pm 7.0
Legal-XLM-R _{Large}	85.51 \pm 1.7	85.76 \pm 0.3	89.58 \pm 1.8	80.16 \pm 4.0	85.25 \pm 4.1
Mean F1 by dataset	86.31 \pm 3.2	83.23 \pm 3.5	85.05 \pm 10.4	73.05 \pm 10.3	81.91 \pm 9.3

Table 5: Multilingual zero-shot experiments within our legal datasets. Each column represents a different set of test and train data where the test data includes all legal datasets in languages that are not the language of the test dataset.

seem to have an advantage over the other *LMs*. The best results were achieved by the XLM-R_{Base} model. All models, except for DistilmBERT, performed significantly better than in the previous experiment across all datasets. DistilmBERT performed worse on the German datasets than in the previous experiment. One explanation for this might be that DistilmBERT is the only cased model used in our experiments. In general, cased models perform better than uncased models, but this does not seem to apply to cross-lingual experiments. Similar results were found by Macková and Straka [21], who conducted cross-lingual reading comprehension experiments from English to Czech and found that the uncased models outperformed the cased models in these experiments. They theorized that the overlap of sub words is bigger between English and Czech for uncased models because they disregard diacritical marks, which are common in Czech. A similar argument could be made for the cross-lingual transfer between Italian, French and German, because German includes a lot of casing information while Italian and French do not.

5.3 MULTILINGUAL EXPERIMENTS

The highest test results for negation scope resolution on our legal datasets were achieved by training our models on the entirety of the available data (Table 6). This multilingual approach achieved an average F1-score of 90% across all models and datasets and outperformed all of the previous setups. This indicates that a relatively small amount of training data in the domain and language of the test dataset can significantly improve the performance of a language model (*LM*). It is also notable that there seems to be no substantial difference in the performance of the different *LMs* in this experiment, with a standard deviation of only ± 3.6 over all models and datasets. Although

Model	Test Dataset				Mean F1 by Model
	fr	it	de(DE)	de(CH)	
DistilmBERT	87.54 \pm 0.6	82.90 \pm 1.3	94.63 \pm 0.5	90.77 \pm 1.2	88.96 \pm 4.5
mBERT	89.98 \pm 2.1	83.72 \pm 1.0	95.21 \pm 0.5	87.83 \pm 1.0	89.10 \pm 4.4
XLm-R _{Base}	91.31 \pm 1.2	88.81 \pm 1.1	94.74 \pm 0.7	89.39 \pm 1.8	91.06 \pm 2.6
XLm-R _{Large}	90.77 \pm 1.8	87.44 \pm 0.5	93.40 \pm 1.1	90.20 \pm 3.9	90.45 \pm 3.0
Glots500-m	89.65 \pm 1.0	85.54 \pm 2.3	94.94 \pm 0.7	91.00 \pm 2.7	90.28 \pm 3.8
Legal-Swiss-R _{Base}	89.08 \pm 1.6	87.40 \pm 1.9	94.60 \pm 1.0	87.02 \pm 1.5	89.52 \pm 3.4
Legal-Swiss-R _{Large}	89.07 \pm 1.4	86.72 \pm 1.5	95.94 \pm 0.2	89.39 \pm 0.9	90.28 \pm 3.7
Legal-XLm-R _{Base}	90.71 \pm 0.5	86.67 \pm 0.5	95.41 \pm 0.7	86.17 \pm 2.4	89.74 \pm 4.0
Legal-XLm-R _{Large}	90.75 \pm 1.4	89.46 \pm 0.8	93.87 \pm 0.8	89.18 \pm 1.0	90.82 \pm 2.1
Mean F1 by Dataset	89.87 \pm 1.2	86.52 \pm 2.4	94.74 \pm 1.0	88.99 \pm 2.4	90.03 \pm 3.6

Table 6: Results from multilingual experiments over all available data.

DistilmBERT obtained the lowest scores in this experiment, its performance is not significantly inferior to that of the mBERT model. This could be attributed to the fact that the training data for this experiment also included German examples which might have mitigated the advantage of the uncased models with regard to shared vocabulary. We also conducted multilingual experiments only using our new datasets which achieved very similar results with an overall F1-score of 89.1 \pm 4 (See Appendix A.3)

5.4 CHATGPT

We evaluated the performance of ChatGPT-3.5, one of the leading LMs, in the task of negation scope resolution on our legal datasets. Other researchers have found that ChatGPT performs well on simple annotation tasks such as text classification [14]. To analyze ChatGPT’s understanding of negation scopes, we conducted a small test over the chat interface (See Appendix A.1) which showed that it was able to correctly identify the negation scope of a simple German sentence. For the same request with an example sentence from our legal dataset, ChatGPT was not able to accurately identify the negation scope. To evaluate the performance on the whole dataset, we used the ChatGPT API with ‘gpt-3.5-turbo-16k’ to accommodate longer inputs and set the temperature to 0 to reduce randomness and receive a coherent output in json format. Similar to the experiments with the NegBERT architecture, we gave the sentence as well as the labels for negation cues as input and prompted ChatGPT to return the sentence annotated for negation scopes. In a zero-shot experiment, we did not give any annotated examples and only provided a short definition of negation scopes. The results show that ChatGPT’s performance on our datasets is subpar (Table 7). In an effort to increase the performance, we conducted some few-shot experiments where 1, 5 or 10 examples of annotated sentences were provided with the prompt but this did not improve the results. The results of the 1-shot experiments averaged lower than the 0-shot experiments. Overall the standard deviation is very high which can be

explained by the fact that a random set of annotated examples was selected for each of the five experiment runs. Overall we can conclude, that ChatGPT is currently not suited to solve negation scope resolution in the legal domain.

Test Dataset	0-shot	1-shot	5-shot	10-shot	Mean F1 by Model
fr	13.00 \pm 2.1	16.63 \pm 10.3	14.90 \pm 7.5	22.53 \pm 10.7	16.77 \pm 8.5
it	25.11 \pm 1.5	18.22 \pm 6.5	31.07 \pm 7.1	26.10 \pm 3.8	25.12 \pm 6.7
de (DE)	16.47 \pm 2.6	22.45 \pm 9.1	17.34 \pm 2.7	24.48 \pm 10.7	20.18 \pm 7.5
de (CH)	32.91 \pm 7.9	21.20 \pm 5.8	36.89 \pm 18.6	19.83 \pm 10.3	27.71 \pm 13.1
Mean F1 by experiment	21.87 \pm 8.9	19.62 \pm 7.8	25.05 \pm 13.6	23.23 \pm 8.9	

Table 7: Results for zero- and few-shot experiments conducted over the ChatGPT API.

ERROR ANALYSIS

We investigated the length of the predicted negation scopes as well as random samples of the predictions on the French and German test data to identify some common error cases.

6.1 PREDICTED SCOPE LENGTH

As expected, our cross-domain zero-shot experiments that did not include any legal training data achieved the lowest F1-scores overall. This can mostly be attributed to the differences in annotation for each dataset, as well as the different domains. Although the external corpora included French data, this did not improve the performance on the fr dataset compared to the other legal datasets. A possible reason is that the subject was not annotated as part of the scope in the Dalloux dataset opposed to the fr dataset.

Figure 3: Actual scope length and predicted scope length by Legal-XLM-R_{Large} for four different experiments. X marks the scope length of the train data for each experiment.

An analysis of the predicted scope length compared to the actual scope length reveals one main issue with the zero-shot transfer from the external datasets of different domains to our legal datasets. Figure 3 shows the analysis of the predicted scopes by the Legal-XLM-R_{Large} model. In our cross-domain

zero-shot experiment, the predicted scope length is significantly shorter than the actual annotated scope length. This can be explained by Table 2 which shows that the annotated scope length of the external datasets (24%) is shorter than the scope length in our legal datasets (38.6%). This issue can also be verified by analyzing some sample predictions which show that the model did not annotate the subject as part of the scope.

Annotation : Es sei festzustellen, dass der Rückerstattungsanspruch **nicht** verjährt sei.

Annotation: *It should be noted that the claim for restitution is not forfeited.*

Prediction : Es sei festzustellen , dass der Rückerstattungsanspruch **nicht** verjährt sei.

Prediction: *It should be noted that the claim for restitution is not forfeited.*

We can see that as soon as some legal data is added to our training sets, the predicted scope length as well as the F1-score increases. An inspection of the predictions made by the legal and multilingual models shows that the additional training data helps to identify the subject in the sentence and predict it as part of the scope. One exception where the subject was not annotated in the prediction is for subjects represented by the initial of a name instead of a pronoun or a full name, which is common in legal documents for anonymization reasons. We suspect that in these cases the models were not able to identify the initial as the subject because these kinds of subjects might be more uncommon outside of the legal domain.

Annotation: E. ne disposait d'aucune autonomie budgétaire;

Annotation: *E. had no budgetary autonomy*

Prediction: E. ne disposait d'aucune autonomie budgétaire;

Prediction: *E. had no budgetary autonomy*

6.2 NON-CONTINUOUS COPES

Another error case is sentences where the scope is not continuous because it is interrupted by an interjection or contrasting statement. These kinds of sentences are more complex than the average sentence and not very common in the training data. A larger amount of training data containing similar sentence structures might increase the accuracy of these predictions.

Annotation: Eine ordentliche Kündigung ist während der vereinbarten Laufzeit beiderseits nur zum Vertragsende und nicht zu einem früheren Zeitpunkt zulässig.

Annotation: *An ordinary termination during the agreed term is only permissible on both sides at the end of the contract and not at an earlier time*

Prediction: Eine ordentliche Kündigung ist während der vereinbarten Laufzeit beiderseits nur zum Vertragsende und nicht zu einem früheren Zeitpunkt zulässig.

Prediction: *An ordinary termination during the agreed term is only permissible on both sides at the end of the contract and not at an earlier time*

LIMITATIONS AND ETHICS STATEMENT

7.1 LIMITATIONS

Due to resource constraints, the datasets we produced are relatively small compared to other publicly available corpora. A larger set of legal data across a diverse set of sources, annotated with negations could further improve the performance of LMs for negation scope resolution in this field. We also did not investigate the potential of cross-lingual cue detection since this is the more trivial part of negation research and can easily be replaced by a list of negation cues for each language.

7.2 ETHICS STATEMENT

The goal of our work was to improve the performance of negation scope resolution systems in the legal domain. These improved systems could be used to support legal professionals in processing and analysing legal texts. These systems should only be used as an assistance to human experts with considerations to their limitations and possible biases. To the best of our knowledge there is currently no real world application of a negation scope resolution system in the legal domain.

The legal data that we annotated and used to train our models is all publicly available and has all been anonymized. It should therefore not include any sensitive information.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

8.1 CONCLUSION

We released new legal datasets in German, French and Italian, annotated for negation cues and scopes and showed that the legal domain does pose a challenge for models in negation scope resolution. Cross-domain zero-shot experiments showed that models without legal training data do not perform as well on multilingual legal datasets as they do on other domains. The task is also too complex for ChatGPT, which was not able to reach F1-scores above 37%. Using our new datasets we finetuned different models on the legal domain significantly improving the results and showing that even relatively small amounts of training data in a specific domain and language can improve the performance of multilingual LMs for negation scope resolution.

8.2 FUTURE WORK

Models performing negation scope resolution in the legal domain could benefit from more training data to increase the accuracy for predictions of more complex sentence structures such as non-continuous negation scopes. More diverse data from different legal fields could further improve the performance of negation scope models in the legal domain.

With our new datasets we were able to show that existing systems which perform well on datasets across different domains are not necessarily able to perform as well on legal data. This should motivate future work to focus on this complex domain and evaluate the performance of existing systems in diverse NLP tasks.

APPENDIX

A.1 CHATGPT TEST

User: In the following German sentence give me a list of all words that are part of a negation scope. Negation scope describes all words affected by a negation in a sentence. Format the output as json. Sentence: Ich weiss nicht was eine Kartoffel ist.

ChatGPT: Certainly, here's the JSON output for the words that are part of the negation scope in the provided German sentence:

```
1  {
2  "Neg_scope": [
3      "weiss",
4      "was",
5      "eine",
6      "Kartoffel",
7      "ist"
8  ]
9  }
```

User: In the following German sentence give me a list of all words that are part of a negation scope. Negation scope describes all words affected by a negation in a sentence. Format the output as json. Sentence: Die Gewährung der tariflichen Leistungen, somit auch die Versorgungszusage, die laut Tarifvertrag für Auszubildende nicht gelte, hätte überhaupt nur dann Sinn gemacht, wenn die Versorgungszusage entgegen des Geltungsbereichs des Tarifvertrages auch dem Auszubildenden erteilt hätte werden sollen.

ChatGPT: Certainly, here's the JSON output for the words that are part of the negation scope in the provided German sentence:

```
1  {
2  "Neg_scope": [
3      "gelte"
4  ]
5  }
```

A.2 MEAN RESULTS OVER ALL MODELS, DATASETS AND EXPERIMENTS

Model \ Test Dataset	Zero-shot cross-domain	Zero-shot cross-lingual	Multilingual - legal data	Multilingual - all data	Mean F1 by model
DistilmBERT	61.78 \pm 3.77	66.46 \pm 13.33	0.87 \pm 0.05	88.96 \pm 4.51	72.40 \pm 14.54
mBERT	63.34 \pm 6.24	80.33 \pm 7.10	0.89 \pm 0.04	89.19 \pm 4.41	77.62 \pm 12.33
XLM-R _{Base}	66.98 \pm 4.02	86.71 \pm 3.25	0.90 \pm 0.03	91.06 \pm 2.63	81.59 \pm 11.07
XLM-R _{Large}	70.03 \pm 4.98	85.87 \pm 6.44	0.90 \pm 0.04	90.45 \pm 3.00	82.12 \pm 10.10
Glott500-m	61.30 \pm 4.85	84.50 \pm 5.36	0.89 \pm 0.04	90.28 \pm 3.84	78.70 \pm 13.46
Legal-Swiss-R _{Base}	66.05 \pm 7.72	82.79 \pm 7.41	0.88 \pm 0.05	89.52 \pm 3.41	79.45 \pm 11.82
Legal-Swiss-R _{Large}	68.89 \pm 10.80	81.83 \pm 7.81	0.90 \pm 0.03	90.28 \pm 3.66	80.33 \pm 11.84
Legal-XLM-R _{Base}	66.57 \pm 9.33	83.44 \pm 7.01	0.90 \pm 0.04	89.74 \pm 3.99	79.92 \pm 12.10
Legal-XLM-R _{Large}	71.59 \pm 7.73	85.25 \pm 4.07	0.89 \pm 0.04	90.82 \pm 2.12	82.55 \pm 9.61
Mean F1 by experiment	66.28 \pm 7.64	81.91 \pm 9.26	0.89 \pm 0.04	90.03 \pm 3.57	

Table 8: Mean Results over all models and experiments

A.3 MULTILINGUAL RESULTS LEGAL DATA

Model \ Test Dataset	fr	it	de (DE)	de (CH)	Mean F1 by Model
DistilmBERT	86.06 \pm 0.76	81.82 \pm 0.79	93.98 \pm 0.82	87.40 \pm 2.36	87.32 \pm 4.65
mBERT	90.16 \pm 1.33	84.56 \pm 1.63	94.95 \pm 0.80	86.81 \pm 2.06	89.12 \pm 4.25
XLM-R-Base	90.26 \pm 0.96	88.05 \pm 1.81	94.12 \pm 0.59	87.21 \pm 2.66	89.91 \pm 3.16
XLM-R-Large	90.23 \pm 1.40	86.93 \pm 0.73	94.56 \pm 0.85	86.44 \pm 3.56	89.54 \pm 3.80
Glott500-m	88.81 \pm 1.47	85.62 \pm 1.12	94.23 \pm 1.40	88.13 \pm 2.60	89.20 \pm 3.59
Legal-Swiss-R-Base	87.98 \pm 1.46	89.53 \pm 0.54	93.15 \pm 0.44	81.82 \pm 3.88	88.12 \pm 4.62
Legal-Swiss-R-Large	88.35 \pm 0.88	88.20 \pm 1.13	95.30 \pm 0.37	89.39 \pm 1.37	90.31 \pm 3.13
Legal-XLM-R-Base	88.89 \pm 1.58	88.41 \pm 1.84	95.56 \pm 0.88	85.27 \pm 3.83	89.53 \pm 4.39
Legal-XLM-R-Large	88.86 \pm 0.95	87.98 \pm 0.64	94.46 \pm 0.69	85.30 \pm 3.12	89.15 \pm 3.76
Mean F1 by dataset	88.84 \pm 1.70	86.79 \pm 2.55	94.48 \pm 1.01	86.42 \pm 3.36	89.13 \pm 3.97

Table 9: Results of multilingual experiments using only our legal datasets.

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